

The use of distance technologies in Rural Education in the context of the development of a system for assessing the quality of teaching

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ABSTRACT. The main purpose of the article is to study the main qualities of the use of distance technologies in rural education in the context of COVID-19 in the context of the development of a system for assessing the quality of teaching. Distance and blended learning technologies have become familiar to the rural education system during the years of the coronavirus pandemic. The State Service for the quality of teaching in different countries has also adapted the tools for conducting institutional audits to the conditions of remote work or partially remote work. Adaptation requires the organization of rural educational activities so that institutions continue to work efficiently and effectively both in full-time and online learning. All components of the system of the educational process of rural education should also be changed, including finding new ways to assess the quality of teaching.

Keywords: pedagogy, quality of teaching, rural education, coronavirus pandemic, distance education.

O uso de tecnologias a distância na Educação do Campo no contexto do desenvolvimento de um sistema de avaliação da qualidade do ensino

RESUMO. O objetivo principal do artigo é estudar as principais qualidades do uso de tecnologias à distância na educação rural no contexto da COVID-19 no contexto do desenvolvimento de um sistema de avaliação da qualidade do ensino. As tecnologias de ensino à distância e misto tornaram-se familiares ao sistema de Educação do Campo durante os anos da pandemia do coronavírus. O Serviço do Estado para a qualidade do ensino em diferentes países também adaptou as ferramentas para a realização de auditorias institucionais às condições de trabalho remoto ou trabalho parcialmente remoto. A adaptação requer a organização de atividades educativas rurais para que as instituições continuem a trabalhar de forma eficiente e eficaz, tanto em tempo integral como na aprendizagem online. Todos os componentes do sistema do processo educacional da Educação do Campo também devem ser alterados, inclusive encontrando novas formas de avaliar a qualidade do ensino.

Palavras-chave: pedagogia, qualidade do ensino, educação do campo, pandemia do coronavírus, educação à distância.

El uso de tecnologías a distancia en la educación rural en el marco del desarrollo de un sistema de evaluación de la calidad de la enseñanza

RESUMEN. El artículo tiene como objetivo principal estudiar las principales cualidades del uso de las tecnologías a distancia en la educación rural en el contexto del COVID-19 en el contexto del desarrollo de un sistema de evaluación de la calidad de la enseñanza. Las tecnologías de aprendizaje a distancia y combinado se han vuelto familiares para el sistema educativo rural durante los años de la pandemia de coronavirus. El Servicio Estatal para la Calidad de la Docencia en diferentes países también ha adaptado las herramientas para realizar auditorías institucionales a las condiciones del trabajo a distancia o parcialmente a distancia. La adaptación requiere la organización de actividades educativas rurales para que las instituciones continúen trabajando de manera eficiente y efectiva tanto en el aprendizaje a tiempo completo como en línea. Todos los componentes del sistema del proceso educativo de la educación rural también deben cambiarse, incluso encontrar nuevas formas de evaluar la calidad de la enseñanza.

Palabras clave: pedagogía, calidad de la enseñanza, educación rural, pandemia de coronavirus, educación a distancia.

Introduction

A modern rural school is an educational organization located in a rural area, including in the socio-cultural situation of the settlement in which it is located and performing, in addition to teaching, cultural, educational, and social functions. The educational process of a rural school is characterized by dependence on a complex of interrelated external and internal factors that have both direct and indirect influences on its implementation and contribute to or complicate the solution of educational problems.

External factors include type of settlement, type of educational institution, socio-cultural situation, location of the school, availability of institutions of additional education, and culture.

The internal factors that determine the characteristics of the educational process of a rural school include the number of students, which affects the development of student's communication skills, the level of motivation for learning, the organization of the educational process; a high degree of dependence on the level of qualifications of teachers, due to their lack of alternatives in rural areas; the degree of availability of educational resources, which affects the openness of an educational institution and the level of organization of educational work (Lukyanova, 2020).

Distance learning as a form of education using computer and telecommunication technologies provides interactive interaction between teachers and students at different stages of training and independent work with the materials of the information network. The conditions that were created during the quarantine period, during the global coronavirus pandemic, forced all participants in the educational process to use modern information technologies, regardless of their desire. The practical experience gained by the subjects of the educational process, regardless of gender and age, allowed them to quite deftly master information competencies.

On the other hand, information technology has long become a leading part of our professional and everyday life, so teachers and teachers, of course, have experience in using this convenient tool, regardless of whether learning online or offline (Ratten, 2020).

The provision of high-quality educational services by educational institutions, of course, should, first of all, be regulated by state regulatory documents, where the quality of distance education means a set of properties of the educational system that ensure that students receive knowledge, skills, and abilities that meet certain requirements fixed in state standards of vocational education. This includes monitoring the performance of the

organization for the provision and conduct of the educational process, regulated by the standards of the ISO 9000 series.

However, these normative documents cannot cover all the parameters of learning and guarantee the acquisition of a full range of knowledge and skills that a student must master in the course of the educational process. Therefore, each educational institution should have its own quality management system, including documents, methods, and procedures used in the learning process to achieve the required level of quality of services provided. Based on the basic principles and requirements for traditional forms of education, this system should take into account all the features inherent in a particular educational institution (Tarasova, 2011).

Taking this into account, the main purpose of the article is a theoretical study of the current features of the introduction of distance education into the educational process in the context of post-pandemic consequences on postmodern society.

Methodology

The main purpose of the article is to study the main qualities of the use of distance technologies in rural education in the context of COVID-19 in the context of the development of a system for assessing the quality of teaching. For this, a number of methods were applied, which form the research methodology. The study was carried out using the following theoretical methods (Bansak, & Starr, 2021; Borzenko, 2017; Brazhnik, 2005):

1. Systems analysis and synthesis this is the direction of the methodology of special scientific knowledge and social practice, which is based on the study of objects as systems. The specificity of the system approach is determined by the fact that it focuses research on the disclosure of the integrity of the object and the mechanisms that ensure it, on the identification of various types of connections of a complex object and its construction into a single theoretical picture. The main principles of the systems approach are:

- studying the phenomenon of integrity and establishing the composition of the whole, its elements;

- the study of the patterns of connection of elements in the system, that is, the structure of the object that forms the core of the system approach;

- the study of the functions of the system and its components in close connection with the study of the structure, that is, the structural-functional analysis of the system;

- the study of the genesis of the system, its boundaries, and connections with other systems;

2. Induction and deduction, comparison, classification, generalization and systematization, idealization, and abstraction.

Research Results

Distance education is an open learning system that provides for active communication between a teacher and a student using modern technologies and multimedia. This form of education gives the freedom to choose the place, time, and pace of learning, thanks to the Internet, which covers wide layers of society and becomes an important factor in its development (Borzenko, 2017).

It should be noted that distance learning is not antagonistic to full-time and part-time forms of education. It integrates naturally into these systems, complementing and developing them, which contributes to the creation of a mobile learning environment. The perfect form of distance learning is learning based on the use of global and local computer networks (Internet) (Rack, 2017).

A remote lesson in a rural school, conducted in the format of a videoconference, has a number of organizational features of a traditional lesson, namely: a clear time of the conduct, determined by the school schedule, a standard lesson duration, a specific place for conducting a group form of conducting a lesson, and instant feedback between participants in the educational process. In addition to organizational features, it is possible to single out structural features of a distance lesson that bring it closer to a traditional one. This is an opportunity to conduct lessons of various types: a combined lesson, a lesson in learning new material, a lesson-lecture, a lesson in consolidating knowledge, etc.

A remote lesson in the form of a videoconference allows you to use the traditional stages of the lesson: updating knowledge, repetition, learning new material, consolidation, and reflection. It is also possible to use various forms of work: conducting practical and laboratory work, testing, oral questioning of students, conversations, and written and independent work. At the same time, a remote lesson in the form of a videoconference has a number of additional features compared to a traditional lesson in a rural school. These include (Lunyachek, 2011):

- the use of group forms of work, which is impossible in a small class of a rural school;

- communication with “remote” classmates, which forms communication skills in a virtual environment;

- carrying out virtual laboratory and practical work that cannot be carried out in a rural school due to the lack of necessary equipment and other resources (Burgin, 1997);

- work with electronic educational resources in the "common board" mode, which allows you to create your own multimedia product during the lesson in the form of an interactive presentation or in another form;

- inclusion in the lesson of additional participants - experts studying from other schools, which expands the educational space of the lesson and shows the importance of the material being studied;

 - providing students with access to remote educational resources

 - resources of libraries, museums, and educational portals, which allow enriching the subject content of lessons in a rural school (Brazhnik, 2005).

Laboratory work is intended for the practical assimilation of the material. The laboratory practice is greatly simplified through the use of multimedia technologies, simulation, Internet technologies, and the like. Virtual reality allows students to demonstrate phenomena that are difficult or impossible to show under normal conditions. Distance learning consulting is one of the forms of student management and assistance in the independent study of the discipline. To do this, use e-mail, teleconferences, as well as conventional means of communication (telephone, fax, mail).

Control is a check of the results of theoretical and practical assimilation by a student of educational material. In distance learning, test control has paid off. The tests are well suited for self-control and are very useful for individual practice (Carr & Kemmis, 2005).

Many distance learning models use a certain type of communication as a basis for building a learning system, which is the leading one in a particular model. The type of communication determines such characteristics of distance learning as the synchronism of interaction, the level of interactivity, the structure of the information, and the educational environment.

There are also problems such as:

- lack of personal communication between teacher and student (less effective transfer of knowledge occurs, without personal contact). There is also a lack of communication with fellow students for the exchange of experience;

- the student has the strong personal motivation, and the ability to study independently, without the constant support and push from the teacher;
- lack of the possibility of the immediate practical application of the acquired knowledge, followed by a discussion of the questions that have arisen with the teacher and clarification of the situation with specific examples;
- students are not always able to provide themselves with sufficient technical equipment - to have a computer and a constant Internet connection;
- there are no or very expensive applied computer programs necessary for maintaining WEB-sites and information resources, administration of distance learning processes;
- the need for large investments at the initial stage of organizing the work of the distance learning system.

Distance learning has forced many conservative educators to reconsider their attitude toward the teaching methodology. It became clear that mechanical duplication of information is the least effective way of long-term memorization of educational material and is not the basis for the development of critical thinking in pupils and students. Confirmation of the lack of long-term effectiveness of mechanical reproduction of information was the experiment of Bjork Bretzig and Raymond Kulhavi, which deals with the four least effective types of work (Langedard, Kiani, Nielsen & Svensson, 2021).

To ensure a high quality of education, especially during the critical period of a pandemic, the subjects of the educational process must increase the level of their information competencies, apply the latest scientifically based technologies and methods of educational and cognitive activities; educational institutions - to support this initiative, especially by providing a material base, and pupils and students - to create a demand for it. Compliance with academic integrity and responsibility in distance learning in one way or another universalizes and disciplines the subjects of the educational process. Respectable teachers and professors tried very hard to maintain the pace and quality of teaching during the quarantine: preparing for an online lesson took much more time than during classes in the classroom; translation of some tasks into written format took time and effort to check them (Filipenko, 2016).

Less responsible teachers could not use video communication at all, leaving the responsibility of pupils and students to independently study new topics. This situation raises the question of fair wages, the tariff setting of the academic load and autonomy in determining the level of salaries of an educational institution. Educational institutions felt

the use of plagiarism in the educational process quite sharply during the quarantine. Printing of finished written works, abstracts, term papers from the Internet, falsification of experimental data (Teelken, 2018).

Students and learners who are not accustomed to working virtuously, producing falsified and copied reports, tests, course projects, and qualification papers. Another pressing problem is educators, many of whom do not know or use assessment methods that made student bad practices impossible. Each educational institution must create a system that would help to ensure academic virtue and to shape the appropriate culture of students and pupils (Mair, Battilana & Cardenas 2012).

With regard to independent work, which is a significant share the educational process of students, the advantages persist even from the pre-quarantine period. Working on a personal computer or other gadget makes it possible to search in detail for sources, information, video, and photo files, in accordance with the task of each topic of the discipline that the student is studying. According to the stages of training, the quarantine stage is exactly that emergency situation in which distance learning occurs as a link of continuous interaction between the teacher and the student (Father, 2014).

The advantages of distance communication in the educational process are led by the possibility of teaching material of any discipline in accordance with the abilities and level of training of students through the use of various sites, video lessons, popular science and documentaries, and online tests on the platform of the institution of higher education or other educational links. It is also relevant that distance teaching expands the possibility of introducing the latest technologies, socio-psychological, pedagogical innovative technologies, and methodological developments such as interactive at a convenient time for the teacher and most students, without leaving home, the main place of work, or that place in the world. in which there are participants in the remote process. This teaching method allows you to optimize the education process on the part of the economy and sanitation. The difficult socio-economic situation in the country will undoubtedly affect the budget of both public and private higher education institutions (Dinkelman, 2003).

The absence of the use of classrooms and the work on personal multimedia teaching aids by the student or teacher will significantly ease the economic burden on the educational institution during this period. Also, under quarantine conditions, distance learning complies with all the prescriptions, requirements, and advice of medical personnel and the state rescue service (Lola, 2017). Credit-modular training is reflected in the breakdown of

educational material into separate modules and a list of topics that are studied as mastering and the abilities of each individual student or the entire group. A significant advantage is also the fact that both students attending classroom classes and those who study according to an individual training schedule now have the opportunity to listen to the teacher more often, get advice, and also take part in an interactive discussion, discussion during a video conference. Such work significantly motivates active educational and cognitive activity and improves the efficiency of the educational process. Socio-psychological aspects of distance learning are the ability to control the quality of education of all students, the use of self-control and self-actualization, and the absence of psychological barriers between participants in communication. Among the disadvantages of distance learning is that the teacher plays a triple role: tutor, organizer, and administrator (Cochran-Smith, 2009).

Three stakeholders in the field of higher education faced the problems of rapid adaptation to the conditions of the pandemic: 1) state institutions; 2) students; 3) scientific and pedagogical workers (Bansak & Starr, 2021).

The student body of higher educational institutions has little psychological and organizational difficulties in adapting to distance learning. According to the results of the survey, during a pandemic among students and scientific and pedagogical workers, applicants for higher education are faced with the following problems (Arlinwibowo, Retnawati, Kartowagiran & Kassymova, 2020):

- lack of uninterrupted access to the Internet;
- the risk of biased assessment;
- insufficient self-organization; irregular communication with the teacher;
- lack of necessary equipment at home;
- lack of the necessary skills to work with equipment and remote technologies.

Difficulties of distance learning from the point of view of scientific and pedagogical workers are as follows (Kryshtanovych, Romanova, Koval, Lesko & Lukashevskaya, 2021):

- lack of "live" contact between teacher and student;
- insufficient technical support for the educational process;
- insufficient level of knowledge of the participants in the educational process by means of information and communication technologies;
- the risk of manifestations of academic dishonesty;
- the risk of biased assessment of students;
- lack of perfectly developed online courses;

- the risk of using online courses of dubious quality in the context of an emergency development of the material and the impossibility of its full discussion at a meeting of the department.

Since the quality of distance education in rural areas is directly determined by the quality of information technology, these categories can only be considered in close connection. In the literature, it is proposed to characterize the quality of education with the help of such groups as (Kryshtanovych, Bilyk, Shayner, Barabash & Bondarenko, 2021):

- indicators of the quality of the content of education;
- indicators of the quality of learning technologies;
- indicators of the quality of education outcomes.

Each of these groups corresponds to a number of quality indicators to certain aspects and properties of the provision, organization and conduct of the educational process.

The general concept of the content of education is based on curricula and programs, which are the basic indicators of the quality of the offered educational services and must comply with the existing standards of vocational education; as well as the current state of the subject area and didactic requirements (Borzenko, 2017).

The next group - the base of educational materials - includes such quality indicators as the compliance of the content of the textbook with the approved curriculum; compliance of the volume of material with established standards; correspondence of the content of the textbook to its form; the degree of completeness and modernity of the covered material of the textbook, as well as the method of self-testing provided in it. This also includes expert assessments of the methodological, content, and technological levels of educational material.

A group of indicators for the technical support of distance education identifies the degree of computer equipment in classrooms, compliance with the requirements for a PC for distance education systems, as well as the bandwidth of data transmission channels (Kryshtanovych, Kryshtanovych, Stechkevych, Ivanytska & Huzii, 2020).

Methods and technologies for conducting training sessions in the distance education system include elements of quality that characterize the technologies of interaction between the teacher and the student, as well as between the students themselves. This also includes the implementation of control measures that identify such important indicators of the quality of the learning process as the degree of availability of teachers; convenience of the form of communication in the communicative structures "teacher - student" and "student - student";

and also allow you to identify the objectivity and completeness of testing and evaluating the knowledge of students during control activities (examination and credit sessions, defense of term papers and theses). This takes into account the availability of the necessary hardware and software and tools for the entire cycle of laboratory work and course design.

The indicators of the staffing group reveal the percentage of teachers with doctoral and candidate of science degrees and without a degree; the availability of scientific and/or methodological publications from teachers, and authorship in distance education courses recommended for distribution (Kryshtanovych, Gavrysh, Khltochina, Melnychuk & Salnikova, 2020).

Characteristic organizational support reveals the presence of an automated document management system (often referred to as an electronic dean's office) and a training quality management system, which, in accordance with ISO 9000 standards, is a documentary system that includes a description of the educational institution's policy in the field of quality assurance, as well as documents regulating duties and powers persons involved in quality assurance. In addition, this also includes documentation containing requirements for the distance education resources used and for indicators of the quality of educational materials and procedures of the educational process, action plans for their provision, etc.

Discussions

As a result of the study of the mechanisms of distance technologies in rural education in the context of COVID-19 in the context of the development of a system for assessing the quality of teaching.

It was found that today there are a large number of problematic aspects of the introduction of the distance education system into the rural education system, in particular, there are a large number of problems in the implementation of effective mechanisms for assessing the quality of teaching. In particular, this issue was studied in the works of.

To implement distance learning in rural education, it is necessary to create a material base; train specialists who will be able to implement this technique; fill the educational database with educational and methodological material, and organize a methodology for monitoring and testing knowledge.

The basis of the material base is computers, smartphones, other mobile devices, and mandatory access to the Internet. Specialists implementing distance learning must be proficient in the main specialty (a subject), possess general information technologies and

skills in working with specific software used to implement a distance education project (Kryshtanovych, Bilyk, Shayner, Barabash & Bondarenko, 2021). Given the novelty of the tasks set for teachers of rural education and the insufficient level of their computer and special technological literacy, we note that the regional institutes of postgraduate pedagogical rural education play an important role in preparing teachers of general education schools for the successful implementation of distance learning.

Conclusions

Consequently, Theoretical research shows that distance learning during quarantine and post-pandemic times has far more benefits than traditional teaching. The employment of pupils and students in a homestay has become effective in educational and cognitive activities, self-education, and constructive communication with a mentor. From the point of view of socio-psychological, educational, economic, and sanitary-hygienic factors, distance learning is optimal not only for a single state but also for the entire world community in the context of the spread of a pandemic.

Due to the impact of COVID-19, the higher education system must be transformed and adapted to new conditions. It is necessary to develop new approaches and models of the educational process. The adaptability of students and teaching staff to the specifics of distance learning presupposes the entry of digital and other related skills. Scientific and pedagogical workers should improve their teaching skills, and develop new online courses and programs, taking into account the specifics of distance learning, and the like. Government authorities, dealing with the solution of the problem of distance learning, in particular, have to create appropriate conditions for uninterrupted and high-quality access to the Internet, especially in rural areas. In modern conditions, it is necessary to combine the potentials of public authorities, higher educational institutions, public organizations, and student self-government bodies to ensure an effective educational process and the acquisition of programmatic general and professional competencies by applicants for higher education in full. The issues of improving the technical, economic and organizational working conditions, ensuring the motivation of the work of scientific and pedagogical workers, and providing them with material and non-material incentives for high-quality professional activity deserve special attention.

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